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MANAGERIAL FUNCTIONS WITHIN THE ORGANIZATION**Karimov Muzaffar Abdumalik ugli**

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Abstract: Management is an essential aspect within the economic life of the human beings, which is an organised group activity. It is considered as the essential institution in the modern social organization, noticeable by scientific thought and technical innovations and methods. One or the other form of management is fundamental, wherever human efforts are to be carried out co-operatively to satisfy the needs through some productive activity, occupation or profession. It is the management that regulates the productive activities of the individuals through the co-ordinated use of resources and materials. In order to manage any task, function or an activity within the organization, it is essential to understand the managerial functions of planning, organizing, directing, staffing, co-ordinating and controlling. There are numerous organizations and to ensure that they are advancing towards welfare, productivity and profitability, and to satisfy the needs and requirements of the individuals, the managerial functions should be implemented effectually.

Keywords: Organization, Planning, Organizing, Directing, Staffing, Co-ordinating, Controlling, group activity, occupation, checkpoints.

Introduction: An organization develops in course of time with complications. With increasing complications, management of the business has become a difficult task. The need of existence of management has augmented and recognized. Management is indispensable not only for business concerns but also for production companies, service companies, financial institutions, banks, schools, colleges, training centres, hospitals, hotels, religious bodies, charitable trusts and so forth. This is apparent that every business unit have different goals and objectives. These objectives can be accomplished with the co-ordinated efforts of

several personnel. Management is regarded as an indispensable aspect of the economic life of man, which is an organised group activity. It is considered as the essential institution in the modern social organization, marked by scientific thought and technological modernizations. One or the other forms of management is fundamental, wherever human efforts are to be assumed co-operatively to satisfy wants through some productive activity, occupation or profession (Pal, n.d.).

The managerial functions are planning, organizing, directing, staffing, co-ordinating and controlling. Planning is the process of selecting and developing the best course of action to achieve an objective. It is the keystone of all other management functions. Organizing means, determining the tasks and functions, establishing the structures, distributing resources and developing strategies and approaches. Directing is the function that involves taking command, giving instructions and ensuring that tasks and functions are performed in an adequate manner. Staffing is recruiting of employees in the right positions in accordance to their educational qualifications, skills and experiences. Co-ordinating means maintaining good relationships, unify efforts, promote mutual understanding and obtain concurrence. Controlling is referred to as formal measurement and analysis of actions at established checkpoints (Managing and Supervising Employees, n.d.). It is vital for the management to obtain adequate understanding and skills regarding these managerial functions, to implement them and achieve the desired goals and objectives.

Planning: Planning is the most important and the most prevalent of all management functions. This function bridges the gap between where we are and where we want to be in future. The tasks and functions that are required to bridge this gap is referred to as planning. If people working in groups have to perform effectually, they should know in advance what is to be done, what activities they have to perform in order to do what is to be done, and when it is to be done. Planning is concerned with what, how, and when of performance. It is determining in the present about the future objectives and the courses of action for their achievement. It involves determination of the long and short range objectives; development of strategies and courses of action to be followed for the

achievement of these objectives and formulation of policies, plans and rules for the implementation of strategies and procedures (Pal, n.d.).

The organizational objectives are established by the top management within the framework of its basic purpose and mission, environmental factors, business forecasts, and available and potential resources. These objectives are both long term as well as short term. They are divided into divisional, departmental, sectional and individual objectives or goals. This is followed by the development of strategies and courses of action to be followed at various levels of management and in various segments of the organization. Policies, procedures and rules make provision of the framework of decision making, and the method and order for the making and implementation of these decisions. Every manager performs all these planning functions, or contributes to their operation. In some organizations, particularly those which are traditionally managed and are small, planning is done, but not in a systematic way. The plans may be within the minds of the managers rather than unambiguously and precisely stated, they may be vague but are always present. Planning is the most basic function of management. It is performed in all kinds of organizations by the managers at all levels in the hierarchy (Pal, n.d.).

Planning ensures that work is implemented effectively and efficiently or leads to improvements in the performance of the individuals. It causes a reduction in procrastination, ensures continuity and provides for the intelligent use of resources. It improves the chances of the individuals in carrying out tasks and resulting in satisfaction of having everything under control and being aware of what will be the next step. Planning is proactive and decreases the need to manage from various crisis situations. It is a prerequisite for all the necessary managerial functions, including teaching and mentoring, preparing for and organising committee and staff meetings, carry out performance appraisal discussions, employment interviews, preparation of budgets and numerous other factors. In case of occurrence of losses, due to natural calamities and disasters, planning of activities is considered essential. The individuals, who are carrying out the functions of planning need to make sure that there are not any barriers and impediments within the course of carrying out of job duties (Chapter 3, 2013).

The key elements of planning are vision, mission, goals, objectives, strategy and action. An organization's vision statement should be clear, stimulating and should create a wide scope for the pursuit of new opportunities. The vision of top management in the hierarchy should be wide ranging, so that the vision of subordinates fits within it. An effective mission statement must be expressed clearly in a single and brief paragraph and in a language that everyone can understand. When workers participate actively in the organization of mission statements, then they are able to understand what the purpose of the organization is and what their work is all about. Goals are featured by specific ends or conclusions. Most of the employees prefer activities leading to conclusions. The workforce usually prefer to work on projects, because they have clear objectives rather than getting involved in routine work. The characteristics of the goals should be scrutinized by the individuals, they should be realistic, understandable, measurable, behavioural, achievable and specific (Chapter 3, 2013).

Organizing: Organizing is a comprehensive term, which includes numerous functions, such as, working out the job duties, activities, tasks, presentations, meetings, making use of technology and other innovative methods and ideas and so forth. It is the process of gearing up to implement decisions that result from the planning process. In other words, it is the establishment of the structure, when the work gets done. It involves delineating of the tasks and establishing a framework of authority and responsibility for the people, who are engaged in the performance of the tasks, that is formation of the composition. In addition it involves, analysis of the job duties, distributing it amongst the employees and co-ordination of the activities, so that work is carried out smoothly. Supervisors and leaders are the ones, who perform the function of organizing. This function is performed in an adequate manner, making use of the power and authority that has been assigned to them. Essential organizing tools include, policies, procedures, work rules, position descriptions, and the important activities of assigning and delegating (Chapter 3, 2013).

Directing: Directing is a function of leading the employees to perform efficiently and productively. The main purpose of this function is to make sure the measures that are formulated to achieve the desired and goals and objectives are moving in the right direction. The workforce should have the main aim of dedicating their efforts towards the pursuance of goals and objectives. The subordinates that are recruited, may or may not have some experience, they need to be adequately explained about their job duties. It is the job duty of the supervisors to guide them, train them and solve their problems. It is important for all the members of the organization to work with interest and enthusiasm (Pal, n.d.). These factors would not only lead to the achievement of the desired goals, but individuals are able to generate job satisfaction. The feelings of job satisfaction amongst the individuals are considered vital to retain them in their jobs.

The function of directing involves three sub-functions, these are, communication, motivation and leadership. Communication within the organization takes place in two forms, oral communication, which is through face to face conversation, telephone etc. Written communication, takes place in any written form, it is in the form of emails, messaging, letters, articles, documents, pamphlets, notices etc. Communication is regarded as an integral part for any task or function to get carried out. This takes place amongst the individuals at all the levels of the hierarchy. When superiors need to give instructions to their subordinates, in the case of organization of meetings etc. various forms of communication are put into practice. Motivation is stated as the way of inspiring and stimulating the employees towards their work. There are various methods through which motivation of employees takes place, these are incentives, bonuses, increase in pay, leaves, etc. This is considered an important aspect in all organizations, when the top most management feels that productivity is low and the organization is not performing well. Then employees are communicated about this problem and measures need to get implemented to inspire them to perform their tasks in an appropriate manner.

The occurrence of problems are an integral part of any organization. For instance, when the organization is engaged in production and manufacturing processes and they are not able to satisfy the needs and requirements of the customers in an adequate manner, then

the function of directing needs to get improved. Whether this function is being carried out within the organization in a proper manner, is analysed in accordance to the job duties of the individuals. For the efficient implementation of this function, it is important for the employees to listen and obey their supervisors. In higher educational institutions or even at the workplace, there have been instances, when individuals, find the job difficult and do not pay adequate attention to what their supervisors are telling them. In such cases, the function of directing faces a setback. Therefore, for the effective implementation of this function, it is important to ensure, there is mutual understanding between the members of the organization and strategies and methods are understandable.

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